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Exploring rock phosphate as a calcium and phosphorus source for Wistar rat nutrition

Joshua Terseer Agedeson^{1*}

¹Department of Animal Science, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

*Corresponding: joshuaagedeson@gmail.com

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Abstract

Calcium and phosphorus play fundamental roles in skeletal development and metabolic regulation in livestock. Rock Phosphate (RP), is a naturally occurring calcium-phosphorus rich resource, with a high fluoride content which could trigger fluoride toxicity in livestock. Yet the volatility of fluoride at relatively low temperatures may eliminate this threat. Therefore, this study evaluated the bioavailability of calcium and phosphorus from raw rock phosphate, RRP and heat treated rock phosphate, HTRP in rat diets, against a bone meal control. The evaluation was conducted in seven-week-old hypocalcaemic Wistar rats (n=30, weighing 103.00±14.68 g) individually housed in a stainless steel cages for 10 days in a Completely Randomised Design-CRD (10 rats per treatment). The rats were maintained on a cycle of 12-hour light and 12-hour dark of 10 days with calcium and phosphorus in a modified AIN93G diet supplied by BM, RRP and HTRP, and deionised water supplied ad libitum. Urine samples were collected for calcium and phosphorus analyses and three rats per treatment were sacrificed for whole carcass calcium/phosphorus analyses, femoral morphometric and physical properties. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and analysis of variance at $\alpha 0.05$. Urine calcium and phosphorus levels of rats were not influenced by the diets. Wistar rats fed BM; RRP and HTRP diets on whole carcass dietary calcium were not significantly influenced. However, whole carcass dietary phosphorus of 1.85 mg/g RRP treatment was similar to that of 2.0 mg/g control diet. Femoral trabecular spacing of 675.02±114.32 (μm) in rats fed RRP were higher than 560.49±61.04 (μm) in rats fed control diet. Physical femoral Parameters revealed dietary treatments had no significant ($P>0.05$) impact. In conclusion, calcium and phosphorus from rock phosphate were bioavailable in Wistar rats as evaluated.

Keywords: Heat treated rock phosphate, raw rock phosphate, bone meal, calcium bioavailability, phosphorus bioavailability, Wistar rats

INTRODUCTION

Calcium and phosphorus play fundamental roles in regulating metabolic activities and skeletal development in livestock, which are the two key minerals accounted for in animal diet formulations. Primary dietary calcium sources such as; oyster shell, periwinkle shell, limestone, di-calcium phosphate and bone meal have been identified. Animal bones are also utilised for a variety of purposes, most notably the production of goods like glue, gelatin, ossein, dinner's foot, dicalcium phosphate, fertilizer, and pottery.¹

The use of bone meal (BM) as calcium-phosphorus source for livestock diets has declined due to possible spread of zoonotic diseases, particularly; mad cow disease.²² Rock Phosphate (RP), a naturally occurring calcium-phosphorus rich resource with high fluoride content holds promise as an alternative for BM. There is an abundance of rock phosphate deposit in various West African nations, particularly in Togo, Senegal, the Benin Republic, and Nigeria, with commercial quantities of the mineral present in Imo, Ogun and Sokoto states.² However, its use is restricted due to its high fluorine content. Heat treatment is a method for lowering the

fluoride content in raw rock phosphate. Heat-treated rock phosphate also known as defluorinated or soft rock phosphate, has fluorine contents that are significantly lower than those of raw rock phosphate (RRP).¹ Therefore, the volatility of fluoride at high temperature informed the evaluation of Heat-Treated RP (HTRP) as replacement for BM in rat diets.²¹

Raw Phosphate rock and Heat treated rock phosphate contains approximately the same amounts of calcium and phosphorus as bone meal of about 17% phosphorus and 34% calcium.¹⁸ The use of rock phosphate may have potential benefits for Ca and P bioavailability in nutrient partitioning of Wistar rat.

Histochemical stains are used to differentiate tissue microarchitecture which can be viewed using various imaging software ¹ ImageJ and its plugin BoneJ are increasingly being used in animal science research to quantify morphometric features and microarchitecture of bone and muscle tissue with high precision.^{8, 21} This can be applied to tissue samples such as bone, muscle, fat, liver, kidney, brain, intestine, etc. To assess the nutritional values of rock phosphate and its metabolic fate in wistar rats, this study tests the hypothesis that diets

with fluorine contents in RRP and HTRP may impair bio-availability in Wistar rat whole carcass, soft tissue, urine, serum, fecal and femoral morphometry and histomorphometry integrity. Consequently, it is now necessary to use more safer and alternative calcium and phosphorus supplements.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at the Rat Room in the Department of Animal Science at the University of Ibadan, which is situated at Latitude 7.27 °N and Longitude 3.54 °E.

Rock Phosphate Processing

Rock phosphate ore was obtained between Latitude 6.82 °N and Longitude 3.23 °E of Ifo in Ogun State Nigeria. The ore was extracted, the slurry sent to a flotation plant, its particles were washed and dried, then milled.¹

The rock phosphate used in this study was further ground and sieved through a 200 µm sieve. 1000 g of the raw rock phosphate samples were heated for five hours at varying temperature rates of 10 °C/min up to 600 °C and until the color changed from brownish grey to reddish brown.⁹ Using inorganic geochemical x-ray fluorescence spectrophotometry, calcium and phosphorus were analysed.

Experimental Diets, Rat Housing and Management

Three experimental diets were generated using (corn starch and casein-based purified diets) with each of the three Ca sources (BM, RRP and HTRP) as the sole source of Ca and P as presented in (Table 1). All diet formulations were based on the modified AIN93G/M¹⁹ with deionised water provided *ad libitum*. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) was incorporated in all diets as an indigestible indicator. A dietary Ca content of 3.0 g/kg was maintained in all diets which was the recommended dietary Ca requirement for wistar rats.

30 day-old Wistar rats with average weight of 103±14.68 g at 7 weeks old were sourced and acclimatised for 2 weeks in individual stainless steel wire-bottom cages of 50cm × 31cm × 23cm with ten rats per treatment, randomly assigned to the dietary treatments. Feed intake and body weight were monitored weekly.

The rats were maintained on a cycle of 12-hour light and 12-hour dark and were fed a completely calcium deficient diet (CDD) for 21 days as depletion periods and repleted for 10 days with diet containing BM as (control) RRP and HTRP. Urine samples were collected before termination of the study for calcium and phosphorus analyses following standard procedures and fecal samples according to modified method of.¹⁷

Table 1. Gross Composition of Calcium Deficient Diet, Bone meal, Raw Rock Phosphate and Heat-treated Rock Phosphate Dietary Treatments Fed weanling Wistar rats (%)

Ingredients	CCD	BM	RRP	HTRP
Corn Starch	56.87	53.87	53.87	53.87
Glucose	14.10	14.10	14.10	14.10
Casein	17.00	17.00	17.00	17.00
Soya bean Oil	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
^a Arbocel	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Ca/P sources	0.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Methionine	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
^b Micro Mix Grower	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Common Salt	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26
Titanium	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Magnesium Sulphate	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11
Potassium Phosphate)	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01
Calculated Nutrients				
M.E (kcal/kg)	3538.93	3538.93	3538.93	3538.93
Crude Protein	14.27	14.27	14.27	14.27
Crude Fibre	3.38	3.38	3.38	3.38
Fat	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
Calcium	0.00	1.03	0.52	0.53
Phosphorus	0.00	0.51	0.93	0.93

^aArbocel- a fibrillated lignocellulic fiber concentrate, J. Rettenmaier and Sohne GmbH + Co KG ,Rosenberg,Germany ^bMicro-Mix Growers, Vitamin and Trace Minerals Supplied the following additional Micro and Macro nutrient Premix: Anti-oxidant 120,000.00 mg , Copper 8,500.00 mg, Iodine 1,500.00 mg, Cobalt 300,00 mg, Chlorine chloride 300,000.00 mg, Vitamin A, 10,000,000.00 I.U, E, 20,000.00 mg, Vitamin K3 mg, Vitamin B6 4,000.00 mg, Vitamin B1 3,000.00 mg, B2 5,000.00 mg, , Folic acid 1,000.00 mg, Biotin 50.00 mg, Niacin 45,000.00 mg, Selenium 120.00 mg, Calcium Pantothenate 10,000.00 mg, Iron 120,000.00 mg, Vitamin B12 20.00 mg, Zinc 80,000.00 mg, Manganese 300,000.00 mg, D3 2,000,000.00 I.U, and M.E – Metabolisable Energy (kcal/kg), Calcium deficient diet= CDD; BM= Bone Meal; RRP= Raw Rock Phosphate; HTRP=Heat Treated Rock Phosphate

Bioavailability of calcium and phosphorus in raw rock phosphate and heat treated rock phosphate through total collection method of digestibility procedure and estimated as;

Apparent digestibility for Ca absorption= $\frac{((\text{Ca intake} - \text{total faecal Ca excretion}))}{(\text{Ca intake})} \times 100$

Apparent digestibility for P absorption= $\frac{((\text{P intake} - \text{total faecal P excretion}))}{(\text{P intake})} \times 100$

After the administration of chlordiazepoxide anesthesia, on day 31 of the study, blood was drawn from the heart of 3 rats per treatment and assayed for calcium and phosphorus. Thereafter, the femur was harvested and gently cleaned to remove blood, muscles and connective tissue with scalpel and forceps and wrapped in gauze soaked in saline and each labeled clearly, and stored at a temperature less than 4 °C. All other bones from each rat were totally removed and the remaining carcasses were stored for the assessment of soft tissue minerals. Another set of 3 rats per treatment were euthanised by carbon dioxide overdose and stored in polyethene bags for the assessment of whole carcass calcium and phosphorus concentration. After assessing the femoral mechanical qualities, it was weighed, defatted, aired and oven dried, milled, and reweighed. To measure bone ash, 0.5g aliquots were weighed twice and burnt at 600 °C in a muffle furnace.⁵ Using Olympus cellSens version 1.5 software (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan), microscopic pictures of femoral marrow were obtained. To obtain bone marrow, lateral blade incisions were made to remove the epiphysis, which allowed for the isolation of femoral marrow. After that, the diaphysis was cut in half, and a stainless-steel spatula was used to scrape out the bone marrow. The bone marrow tissue was sectioned, paraffins embedded, fixed in 10% neutral-buffered formaldehyde, and stained with hematoxylin-eosin.¹⁶ Using the BoneJ plugin of ImageJ software (Wayne Rasband, NIMH, Bethesda, MD, USA), the femoral trabecular microstructure was evaluated for real bone volume (BV/TV), trabecular space (Tb.Sp), trabecular thickness (Tb.Th), and number of trabeculae (Tb.N). Additionally, the degree of trabecular bone reabsorption was visually assessed.

Statistical analysis:

Data were subjected to statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) using.²⁰

Means were separated using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) at $\alpha_{0.05}$.

RESULTS

Analysed Chemical Composition of Bone Meal, Raw Rock Phosphate and Heat Treated Rock Phosphate

Chemical analysis of the BM, RRP and HTRP used in this study revealed calcium contents of 34.45%, 17.16% and 17.11% and proportions of phosphorus as 16.88%, 30.95% and 31.62%. The fluoride content of BM was 0.34% and RRP was 6.30% while HTRP was 0.09%, respectively.

Comparative Partitioning of Calcium, Phosphorus in Plasma and Excretory Products and Digestibility of

Wistar Rat Fed Bone meal, Raw Rock Phosphate and Heat Treated Rock Phosphate

The comparative partitioning of calcium and phosphorus in plasma and excretory products; urine, faeces, and digestibility of Wistar rat fed BM, RRP and are presented in Table 2. Urine calcium and phosphorus were not impacted by the different diets ($P>0.05$). Plasma calcium of Wistar rat fed RRP and HTRP diets were similar to the control groups. Also, plasma phosphorus was observed to be significantly ($P<0.05$) impacted in rats fed RRP diets (5.77 mg/dL) when compared to those on the control diet (3.83 mg/dL). Faecal calcium had no significant difference ($P>0.05$) in Wistar rats across all treatments. Similarly, faecal phosphorus of wistar rats fed BM and RRP (0.08 and 0.09 mg/g) were not significantly different ($P>0.05$) when compared to the control treatment (0.03 mg/g). The digestibility of calcium Wistar rats fed HTRP treatment was noted to be higher (84.71%) compared to rats on the control diet (53.71%). Phosphorus digestibility in rats fed HTRP diet was observed to be significantly ($P<0.05$) higher (93.74%) when compared to control and RRP diets (74.13 and 68.20%, respectively).

The effect of BM, RRP and HTRP diets on Calcium and Phosphorus Utilisation and deposition in Anatomical Compartments of Wister rat Whole carcass, Soft tissue, and Femur Calcium-phosphorus

The effect of BM, RRP and HTRP diets on calcium and phosphorus utilisation and deposition in anatomical compartments of Wister rats whole carcass, soft tissue, and femur are presented in Table 3, Figure 1. Wistar rats fed BM, RRP and HTRP diets did not differ in whole carcass calcium ($P>0.05$). Whole carcass phosphorus of rats in the RRP treatment (1.85 mg/g) was similar to the control (2.04 mg/g) but differed ($P<0.05$) from rats on the HTRP (1.15 mg/g). Soft tissue calcium in Wistar rats on the RRP diet (17.55 mg/g) was observed to significantly differ from the control treatment (10.04 mg/g) and the HTRP (9.03 mg/g) group.

Wistar rats across the treatments did not differ in soft tissue phosphorus concentration ($P>0.05$). Femoral calcium of rats fed the RRP and HTRP diets (1.46 and 1.51 mg/g, respectively), were significantly ($P<0.05$) lower compared to the control treatment (1.95 mg/g).

Femoral Morphometry and Histomorphometry in Wistar rats Fed Bone meal and Rock Phosphate Supplemented Diets

Femoral morphometry and histomorphometry in wistar rats fed bone meal and rock phosphate supplemented diets on parameters measured are presented in Table 4. The dietary treatments had no significant ($P>0.05$) impact on femoral morphometry. For femoral histomorphometry, the trabecular thickness in Wistar rats fed HTRP diet was significantly ($P<0.05$) higher (284.11 μm) compared to the control and RRP treatments (204.13 μm and 230 μm , respectively). Femoral trabecular spacing in rats fed RRP (675.02 μm) and HTRP diets (634.89 μm), respectively, were significantly ($P<0.05$) higher when compared to rats fed control diet (560.49 μm). The dietary treatments had no impact ($P>0.05$) on cellular content parameters measured. Trabecular bone tissue of rats fed HTRP diet (10.31%) was significantly

Table 2. Comparative Partitioning of Calcium and Phosphorus in Bone meal, Raw Rock Phosphate and Heat-treated Rock Phosphate in Wistar rats

PARAMETERS	BM	RRP	HTRP	SEM	P-value
Urine					
Calcium (mg/dl)	4.61	4.45	4.28	0.41	0.953
Phosphorus (mg/dl)	12.42	11.31	8.92	1.19	0.497
Plasma					
Calcium (mg/dl)	6.80	7.79	7.25	0.26	13.907
Phosphorus (mg/dl)	3.83 ^b	5.77 ^a	4.28 ^a	0.25	0.000
Faecal					
Ca (mg/g)	0.25	0.23	0.18	0.03	0.582
P (mg/g)	0.08 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.03 ^b	0.01	0.000
Digestibility					
Calcium (%)	53.71 ^b	61.04 ^{ab}	84.71 ^a	5.01	0.019
Phosphorus (%)	74.13 ^b	68.82 ^b	93.74 ^a	2.95	0.000

^{ab} Means with different superscripts on the same row differs significantly (P<0.05)

Table 3. The assessment of BM, RRP and HTRP diets on Calcium and Phosphorus Utilisation and deposition in Anatomical Compartments of Wistar rats

PARAMETERS	BM	RRP	HTRP	SEM	P-value
Whole Carcass					
Calcium (mg/g)	14.06	6.47	17.15	2.47	0.201
Phosphorus (mg/g)	2.04 ^a	1.85 ^a	1.15 ^b	0.13	0.000
Soft Tissue					
Calcium (mg/g)	10.78 ^{ab}	17.55 ^a	9.03 ^b	1.37	0.016
Phosphorus (mg/g)	1.66	1.77	1.88	0.08	0.580
Femur					
Calcium (mg/g)	1.95 ^a	1.46 ^b	1.51 ^b	0.21	0.003
Phosphorus (mg/g)	0.41 ^a	0.34 ^b	0.31 ^b	0.02	0.010

^{ab} Means with different superscripts on the same row differs significantly (P<0.05)

BA= Bone Ash; RRP= Raw Rock Phosphate; HTRP= Heat Treated Rock Phosphate

Table 4. Femoral Morphometry and Histomorphometry in Wistar rats Fed Bone meal and Rock Phosphate Supplemented Diets

Parameters	Bone meal	RRP	HTRP	SEM	P-value
Relative femoral weight (%)	3.22	3.20	3.17	0.01	0.196
Density (g/cm ³)	0.33	0.27	0.27	0.03	0.548
Bone diameter (cm)	0.23	0.23	0.25	0.01	0.409
Bone length (cm)	2.67	2.63	2.60	0.06	0.912
Trabecular thickness (µm)	204.13 ^b	230.19 ^{ab}	284.11 ^a	11.30	0.008
Trabecular spacing (µm)	560.49 ^b	675.02 ^a	634.89 ^a	25.85	0.010
Cellular contents	182.67	322.89	200.11	33.14	1.855
Trabecular bone tissue (%)	7.26 ^b	8.76 ^{ab}	10.31 ^a	0.43	0.010
Bone volume/Total volume (cm ³)	2902.60	2639.63	2739.00	57.18	0.168
Trabecular number	6.33 ^a	6.00 ^{ab}	4.56 ^b	0.31	0.036

^{ab} Means with different superscripts differ significantly at (P<0.05)

RRP= Raw Rock Phosphate; HTRP=Heat Treated Rock Phosphate

($P < 0.05$) higher when compared with those fed control diet (7.26%). No significant difference ($P > 0.05$) was observed in the bone volume/Total volume of Wistar rats across the different treatments. Meanwhile, trabecular number of rats fed control diet (6.33) was observed to be significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher when compared to HTRP diet (4.56).

Femoral microarchitecture of Wistar rats

Wistar rats fed supplemental diets containing calcium deficient diet showed abnormal bone formation characterised by osteocytes (black arrow), a few osteoblasts (blue arrow), and osteoclasts (red arrow) (Figure 2). After being depleted for 21 days, the rats developed hypocalcaemia, as shown in plate 1. During repletion

periods, it was observed that calcium and phosphorus retention was improved as illustrated in RRP and HTRP treatments due to normal bone formation characterised by osteocytes (black arrow), a few osteoblasts (blue arrow) and osteoclasts (red arrow) as shown in plate 3 and 4, implying bioavailability of calcium and phosphorus in RRP and HTRP.

DISCUSSION

Results of calcium, phosphorus and fluoride content of bone meal from this research were similar to reports of.¹ However, calcium in RRP and HTRP in the current study was lower than reported by the same author. Nevertheless, phosphorus and fluoride contents were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher compared to the report of.¹ This could

Figure 1. Calcium and Phosphorus Retention within Anatomical Compartments, Extra-cellular Fluids and Excretory Bodies in Wistar Rats

State variables are represented by boxes surrounded by thick solid lines; zero pools are represented by dashed lines; and auxiliary variables are represented by thin lines. Arrows show flows. Ca= Dietary calcium; Dietary P= Dietary Phosphorus; GIT = the gastrointestinal track; Ca faecal =Calcium in faecal ;P faecal= phosphorus in faecal; Dietary; Ca urine = Calcium in urine; Ca Plasma= Calcium in plasma; P Urine = Phosphorus in urine Ca BN = Calcium in bone; P BN = Phosphorus in bone; Ca ST = Calcium in soft tissue; P ST = phosphorus in soft tissue; WC = whole carcass

CDD

BM

RRP

TRP

Figure 2. Femoral microarchitecture of Wistar rats

CDD: There is abnormal bone formation characterized by osteocytes (black arrow), a few Osteoblasts (blue arrow) and osteoclasts (red arrow) HE x 400

BM: There is normal bone formation characterised by normal osteocytes (black arrow), a few Osteoblasts (blue arrow) and osteoclasts (red arrow) HE x 400

RRP: There is normal bone formation characterized by normal osteocytes (black arrow), a few Osteoblasts (blue arrow) and osteoclasts (red arrow) HE x 400

TRP: There is moderate atrophy of trabecular bone and increased osteoblasts activity during

be attributed to different sources from geographical locations. The calcium and phosphorus analyses from this study agreed with the report of.⁹

Urinary calcium and phosphorus of rats on the treatments did not differ indicating adequate Ca and P in the diets that were able to aid normal reserves in the body of the test subjects. The result agreed with the report of¹¹ on urine calcium and phosphorus retention of rats.

According to¹², the difference in plasma Ca during depletion, disappeared in the repletion period, and could no longer be differentiated. The repletion period did not influence plasma Ca concentration. Plasma Ca concentration could not be differentiated between pigs fed deficient diet and during the repletion period. The report of¹² were similar with the outcome of this study as plasma calcium did not differ ($P>0.05$) among treatments groups. In the current study, plasma phosphorus activity could be observed to follow similar trend of plasma calcium. The result from the comparative partitioning of calcium and phosphorus in bone meal, raw rock phosphate, and heat-treated rock phosphate fed to Wistar rats in this study was in lined with the report of⁴ on plasma calcium, especially on rat fed diet with RRP.

Non-significant variation in faecal calcium across treatments suggested that it was used effectively. Nonetheless, it was observed that the treatments had a significant impact on faecal phosphorus. The different dietary mineral concentrations, such as fluoride, may have interfered with the Wistar rats' ability to retain phosphorus in their bodies, which could explain the significant difference ($P<0.05$) between treatments as supported by.¹¹

This study confirms that calcium and phosphorus utilisation in wistar rats can be stimulated by earlier moderate calcium and phosphorus deficiency during a period of repletion. Although the duration of the repletion period was short, those results indicate that the depletion may have induced an impairment of bioavailability mineral during digestibility of feed contents. The observation made in this study aligns with the report of¹² on calcium and phosphorus deficiency, during the period of depleted days and repletion.

According to¹¹, the use of apparent digestibility values in diet formulation limits the ability to build diets appropriately with regard to Ca and P supply. Digestibility of feed containing calcium and Phosphorus in Wistar rat diet was observed to differ significantly among groups. This could be due to the presences of aluminum and fluoride in rock phosphate which agreed with the report of.¹ Who reported the differences that existed among biological values of phosphorus from different types of commercial phosphates with biological value of dicalcium phosphate and commercial de-fluorinated rock phosphate was established. The determination of Ca and P availability in feedstuffs is subject to various factors, including dietary, animal, and experimental influences.¹ Consequently, different bioavailability may be assigned to different feedstuffs, as described by.¹¹ As a result, apparent digestibility values of feed for Ca and P underestimate the amount of nutrients that are really.¹¹ They also added that the use of apparent digestibility values in diet formulation limits the ability to build diets

appropriately with regard to Ca and P supply.

When calculating the Ca and P requirements, it is important to consider that changes in skeletal tissue are not precisely proportionate to lean development due to body partitioning.¹⁰ In line with these authors, the result also agreed with the report of¹³, whose model correctly predicted whole-body calcium depositions, confirming that modern pigs have similar bone and muscle growth; most likely as a result of ongoing selection attempts for leaner carcasses and better growth. Whole-body Phosphorus bone deposition can be regarded as being as accurate as calcium bone deposition due to the forecast accuracy for whole-body Ca and the fact that body P, which is found in bone, is deposited in a fixed ratio with Ca.

The bioavailability of soft tissue phosphorus in Wistar rats fed bone meal, raw rock phosphate and heat-treated rock phosphate diets aligned with the research conducted by¹¹ who reported that the concentration of P in soft tissue is stable. The concentration of Ca and P in skeletal tissue is primarily determined by dietary intake. Even while the retention of P and Ca in soft tissue remained constant, increasing calcium deficient diet led to a corresponding increase in phosphorus bone and calcium bone retention. Similarly, absorbed calcium had to be eliminated in a diet low in P, since the lack of P prevented any of the calcium that was consumed from being used.

Pigs with low levels of calcium and phosphorus can quickly grow new bone mass by compensatory bone mineralization.¹⁰ This suggests that a series of diets with varying P contents can be used to accomplish comparable production goals (such as the same bone mass) using various feeding techniques. The femoral morphometry measured in Wistar rat's has shown that dietary treatments had no significant effect on the parameters evaluated, suggesting that minerals were used efficiently during replacement.

There are few literatures where the effects of hypocalcemia were corroborated by histomorphometry measurements, and these generally show no impact on trabecular bone volume cellular content, especially in Wistar rats. The present analysis in growing rats revealed significant changes in trabecular thickness, trabecular bone volume, trabecular spacing, and trabecular bone tissue. Therefore, it is possible that the effect of hypocalcemia on this parameter could be calcium-phosphorus dependent. Moreover, some studies have used reduced amounts of calcium in the diet, rather than complete absence, as in the present study. The report was supported by findings of¹⁰, who stated that pigs with low calcium and phosphorus levels can quickly replenish bone mass by compensatory bone mineralisation.

Despite several studies on the effects of calcium deficiency on bone health (hypocalcemia), relatively little is known about the ensuing histological alterations in Wistar rats bone formation characterised by; osteocytes, osteoblasts and osteoclasts. Calcium deficiency in Wistar rats produced severe bone alterations characterised by an increase in osteoclasts. These data are consistent with reports of¹⁵ who revealed histomorphometry analyses indicating that hypocalcemia induces

osteoclasts.

CONCLUSION

Calcium and phosphorus from rock phosphate were bioavailable in Wistar rats as a viable alternative to bone meal. During absorption of the rock phosphate, anti-nutritional complexes such as fluoride inhibitors may lead to decreased bioavailability. The threat of nutrient loss to complexes was reduced through the adopted processing method of heat treatment which tends to defluorinate the fluoride contents.

Ethical Approval

University of Ibadan Animal Care and Use Research Ethics Committee approved experimental procedures before the commencement of the study. Approval ID: UI-ACUREC/049-0623/09

Author's contribution

Joshua Terseer AGEDESON. Conceptualization, data collection, writing- original draft and writing review. Olatunbosun ODU Conceptualisation, manuscript reviewer and editing. Oluwafunmilayo O. ADELEYE. Methodology, investigation and data analysis.

Data availability

Data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest that has influenced the content of this publication.

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